

The influence of network marketing on the performance of LQY Agricultural Development Co.

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Abstract

With the continuous development of network technology, on the one hand, people's lifestyles have changed a lot. On the other hand, business activities also face new challenges because of the Internet. Various industries are linked to information technology. The use of Internet technology for management has been an important way for many enterprises to manage. At the same time, traditional industries are facing many challenges while developing rapidly. The use of the Internet for planning and marketing has also become an important marketing tool for traditional enterprises. Internet marketing, with its unique characteristics of efficient communication, convenience, and interaction, has shown its unique value in the field of marketing. This paper uses the traditional enterprise's Internet marketing as the research object and is combined with the actual case for the study to demonstrate. During the study, the author uses the law of literature, case analysis, data analysis, and other scientific research methods, through typical case studies, in order to find the problem, from Internet marketing to enterprise sales. Starting from the actual situation of the enterprise, this paper finds out the advantages and disadvantages of the enterprise through the analysis of the organizational structure, production, sales, brand, and other aspects of the enterprise and further discovers the problems of the enterprise by combining the relevant theories of marketing and network marketing. Then, from the actual situation of the enterprise, analyze the marketing model and the development status of the enterprise, as well as the existing problems under the current model, find out the reasons for the formation of the problem, and put forward reasonable suggestions based on the problem. This paper will conduct research on the agricultural enterprise and, through analyzing a sample of the company's marketing case and using the data from the business for many years, analyze the marketing effect. With the analysis of the enterprise and the management data contrast, we can clearly find that changes in the network marketing methods have a remarkable effect. It further provides ideas for traditional enterprises to carry out internet marketing. Finally, the paper combines the enterprise analysis and practice results to summarize the research results of the paper, and from this research and summary, the authors found some problems and put forward their own suggestions for the reference of relevant enterprises.

Keywords: *Influence; Network marketing; Performance.*

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Introduction

As an agricultural country, China is very rich in agricultural products, but at the same time, the competition in the agricultural market is becoming more and more fierce. Some agricultural producers or participants still stay in the traditional marketing mindset, which leads to a lag in marketing strategy and

product sales. Sales activities with traditional sales methods and sales thinking have not adapted to the current situation. The marketing model of agricultural products based on the Internet has been one of the key ways to promote the sales of agricultural products and improve the market competitiveness of agricultural product marketing enterprises.

With the rapid improvement of agricultural productivity, the market size of agricultural products is also expanding. Agricultural products, on the one hand, have a large output and are rich products. On the other hand, there is fierce market competition; the supply of many products is greater than the demand. This market situation brings more challenges to the sales of agricultural products.

In this context, many high-quality, powerful large agricultural products companies closely follow the market, use the Internet to develop and grow, and in all aspects of production and sales, form a unique management model. However, there are still some agricultural enterprises still experience lack of a reasonable marketing model, a lack of talent, an inadequate economic budget, and other reasons. Although there are good products, the sales situation is not ideal. In this context, this paper will choose a typical enterprise as the research object, with Internet marketing as the research content, hoping to provide help to relevant personnel.

Literature Review

The status of enterprises before the introduction of Internet marketing

Research on the current situation of the enterprises is carried out mainly through the following contents, including the basic situation of enterprises, human resources situation, organizational structure, management mode, marketing mode, marketing data, and other aspects. Through the study of the current situation of the enterprise, we can gain a more specific understanding of the business model, production situation, and marketing situation, which will help us further identify the problems of the enterprise and provide targeted marketing solutions.

First, a person needs to understand the company's business situation before using Internet marketing. Through the research of the sample company, we can know that before the Internet marketing, this enterprise was still a relatively traditional agricultural enterprise. Still using traditional marketing is the production and sales of this basic marketing concept due to the characteristics of the enterprise industry. Most of the practitioners are very traditional staff; the management of enterprise management thinking is relatively conservative; and a default habit pattern is formed. This area of marketing planning is relatively weak or does not receive enough attention. Enterprise managers, in the process of managing the enterprise, pay too much attention to agricultural production but ignore marketing planning. In terms of product sales, it still relies on traditional stores and wholesale sales by setting up sales centers and accumulating wholesalers and retailers for sales. The lack of marketing planning in enterprises eventually leads to slow sales of products, long lead times, slow payment recovery, and low production value for enterprise-side businesses.

Through the investigation and analysis, we found that the problems being faced by the company and other many similar enterprises are problems; in the fixed management model, the operation system is relatively mature but did not keep pace with the times, in the face of the competitive market environment, not well for change. For the situation of the research enterprise, before the implementation of Internet marketing programs, the main problems include the following:

Enterprise organization: as an agricultural production enterprise, the original talent structure is production-oriented, taking product quality as the first priority and ignoring the importance of marketing. Resulting in the enterprise's organizational structure and the Internet marketing system not being synchronized. First of all, there is a lack of marketing talents; the enterprise does not have professional

marketing staff, only traditional salesmen or saleswomen; staff turnover is relatively fast; and salesmen often change. The location of the farm is far away from downtown; all employees are working on the farm; life is not convenient. The lack of a dynamic salary distribution principle and the basic fixed salary of employees in each department make it impossible to dispatch employees' motivation, and salesmen lack incentives to accomplish more sales goals. Due to a lack of training systems, employees do not understand the knowledge of network marketing, and there is no good channel to learn. While the application of network products and network platform learning is insufficient, the promotion of network marketing has a certain resistance.

In terms of marketing methods, traditional marketing modes are still adopted. In the actual marketing stage of agricultural products, most of the agricultural products suppliers still adopt traditional marketing methods, such as store orders and independent delivery, which are also the main sales methods, and do not adopt modern marketing channels such as television marketing and internet marketing, which makes it difficult to meet the quality demand of agricultural products and cannot improve the sales volume of agricultural products suppliers (Jiang & Sun, 2020).

Modern information technology is developing rapidly, and new marketing methods are emerging, but on the other hand, such traditional enterprises are still limited to traditional media, such as television and newspapers, in the promotion of agricultural products. Nowadays, people are increasingly away from traditional media. This will lead to an overall publicity effect, and publicity quality will be more seriously affected.

Lack of feedback mechanism in the service process; enterprises lag behind the feedback of consumer demand; lack of effective communication methods; still rely on telephone communication; low efficiency; slow time; feedback is not timely. If a person wants to improve performance, he or she must learn according to feedback. The customer decides whether the service is good or not, so the most important feedback is the feedback from the customer (Gray & Wal, 2012). So, the more contact you have with customers, the clearer things will become, and the clearer you will know what to do. Enterprises should learn to actively communicate with customers, understand customer needs, and establish a feedback mechanism.

Corporate culture: corporate culture has become a stumbling block to Internet marketing. Due to the characteristics of the company itself, agricultural enterprises have less contact with the emerging marketing model and are slower to accept information, and some agricultural operators and managers have not yet realized the importance of Internet technology for marketing agricultural products, resulting in traditional production operators' production and management concepts being relatively traditional and unable to jump out of the inherent model. Managers are accustomed to the traditional way of selling agricultural products, and their concept is old-fashioned, so their acceptance of the new marketing model is low, and their enthusiasm to participate in this new marketing model is not strong. In actual Internet marketing, it is often necessary to carry out full marketing and integrated marketing in order to achieve the flow effect, which requires employees to personally participate in shooting small videos for sharing, but in the enterprise, it is difficult to do this without the corresponding corporate culture.

The enterprise as an agricultural production enterprise and other industries are very different; the products have seasonality, resulting in several months of the year in the off-season without any product sales revenue. This company is a very common organization in the enterprise management mode, which is more traditional; for many years, agricultural production and agricultural products sales were done on the simple route, with an emphasis on product quality, but the enterprise brand packaging, marketing construction, and sales processes relied on experience and intermediaries. The management concept is relatively backward. In the process of development, the company has established a traditional division of labor and collaboration system, and in the process of production activities, the organization, the process, the management, and the thinking are solidified. However, such a management model can no longer meet the needs of the market, resulting in a lack of sensitivity to consumer needs and slow feedback to the market.

As a company, we need to provide products and services while catering to the changing market, which means that we need to constantly adjust our framework system and seek innovation to adapt to market changes.

Network marketing program and implementation

To improve this unfavorable situation, the management decided that reform and innovation must be carried out. The planning plan involves research in many aspects, including consumer markets, project positioning, marketing activities, marketing strategies, sales management, sales services, and other aspects. In today's digital era, mobile Internet has created a marketing ecology that is incomparable to traditional media, which is a network based on user relationships where users can not only actively obtain information but also act as a source of consumption, publish information, and experience and share with more friends. Therefore, the developed marketing plan will be based on the actual situation and problems faced by enterprises, and a new marketing plan is proposed from the perspective of social media marketing, online marketing, and integrated marketing.

The new plan sees Internet marketing as an important way to take advantage of the wide range of Internet communication, fast communication, strong interactivity, and diverse audience groups. Through the use of Internet tools and a series of thematic activities, the rational use of Internet resources, combined with Internet thinking, can be used to design and plan an appropriate marketing plan. This will enhance consumers' interest, interaction and communication, experience, and sharing with consumers, which will in turn enhance consumers' perception of the brand and further increase their awareness of the product.

Optimizing the organizational structure, completing the staffing, and training the corresponding employees in the enterprise are essential to meeting certain requirements. The whole enterprise should have full marketing thinking around the sales team to assist the sales team to complete the target. Through organizational restructuring and talent transformation, marketing talent should understand and use sales tools, and related production and management departments should also be actively involved in customer service.

For the company, no matter what marketing strategy is adopted, its main product is still the most important; the quality of the product is still the core of the company, which is also the basic element of the relationship between supply and demand with the user, based on the existing conditions of the enterprise, through research to increase the number of tourism products, the formation of a product marketing mix, through tourism to drive consumption, and to achieve increased revenue. In addition, in the off-season, the company adopts the cooperative sales model to achieve increased revenue.

In flexible pricing mechanisms, price is an important means of enterprise competition. On the one hand, according to different objectives, choose flexible pricing methods for a variety of corporate products, including tourism services products, to develop a more reasonable and flexible pricing mechanism to support different channels and marketing strategies and to introduce package products or even free products.

Order management includes orders from various channels to monitor the status of orders in a comprehensive and timely manner and to realize the synergy between online and offline channels. Through order management, we can realize inventory management and make timely adjustments to enterprise inventory, including warehouse space management, energy management, and equipment management, to reduce warehouse management costs.

In membership management, through the consumption system, it realizes consumer data integration, achieves omnichannel membership identification and membership service sharing, attracts customers through offline experience, increases new customers through old customer sharing, and finally realizes accurate marketing for online and offline members. Configuring fast cashier equipment in the company's

stores and various service areas can effectively relieve the pressure on the cashier during busy hours in the store and reduce cashier time, while also enhancing the shopping experience of time-sensitive consumers.

Mode selection

The first is to choose the marketing mix with which the enterprise wants to adapt. This program makes comprehensive use of common Internet marketing models, such as direct marketing, relationship marketing, soft marketing, integrated marketing, and portfolio marketing. The Internet and e-commerce have become indispensable marketing methods for enterprises, and it is difficult to achieve the desired marketing effect if enterprises still use a single sales model online or offline. In a mature business model, marketing methods are more diversified, so it is the inevitable trend of the Internet era to change the previous single sales model into a marketing model that integrates online and offline (Cao, 2014).

Enterprises will adopt a combination of offline and online models. The long-term direct marketing carried out by the enterprise will be maintained, but the traditional distribution of leaflets, telephone sales, and other modes will be improved. At the same time, the offline sales channels will be consolidated and developed. For example, the cooperation mode of community small supermarkets will be developed to integrate offline and online resources. In addition, the long-term local brand effect of enterprises can develop corporate customers through the holiday economy, such as corporate holiday welfare and corporate group activities.

Social media, as an important way of network marketing, forms a new sales method, uses networks and social media to attract customers, establishes a solid customer relationship, and improves sales performance. New digital sales technology provides a new way for sales personnel to contact and attract customers in the era of digital and social media. The consumer experience before and after the purchase has become a very important factor affecting the current consumer (Ebrahim et al., 2016).

In the whole design scheme, participation in experience is a key link, and Internet thinking is an important basis for the scheme design, such as the free economy, experience economy, fan economy, and sharing economy. In the interaction and experience, a subconscious idea transmission is formed. In the process of playing, the connection and interaction with consumers are established. The management concept of experience economy holds that a product is an object that consumers experience, and the value of the object is not the value of the object or the product itself, but the value of consumers' experience of the object (Pine & Gilmore, 2013). In addition, participation is also at the core of marketing. The core concept of participation suggests that active forms of participation can help bridge the gap between attitudes and behaviors and build a more lasting relationship between brands and consumers (Hamari et al., 2016).

The free model will be applied in the marketing planning scheme and let everyone experience the freeway so as to improve the brand awareness of the entire enterprise and consumer cognition of the enterprise. Anderson (2009) once said that free is a weapon, and now we know that the most lethal way to enter a market is to completely eliminate the existing business model. For a certain kind of business, other businesses rely on it to make a profit, but if you provide this commodity for free, believe that customers will naturally come to your door.

As digital and social media technologies continue to evolve and consumers become more connected and influential, consumer share marketing has become an important marketing force, and consumers are playing an increasingly important role in shaping brand experiences. While online social media and mobile marketing offer great and exciting opportunities for marketers, most marketers are still learning how to use them effectively. The key is to effectively blend new digital approaches with traditional marketing to create the perfect integrated marketing strategy and marketing mix. In the process of online marketing, companies must pay attention to customer sharing and consumer reviews, because word-of-mouth marketing has a very important role to play in brand influence and product sales. The influence of word-of-mouth has a

great impact on consumer buying behavior. Interpersonal information and recommended web articles from trusted friends, relatives and other consumers are more reliable than information from many commercial sources such as advertisements or salespeople. Research studies have shown that only 49% of consumers say they trust or believe advertising, but 72% say they trust family and friends and online reviews. Emotional engagement occurs when there is a conscious or subconscious connection between the consumer and the brand. Yet behavioral engagement is often seen as a more valuable form of engagement, and interactive media, particularly social media, offers a wealth of previously unknown possibilities for behavioral engagement, while also removing significant barriers that have prevented traditional behavioral engagement.

According to the 7P theory, we can know that the marketing process should take into account the participation of employees, who are important to the overall marketing activities. Employees are the main body of the organization, and everything they do will be part of the customer's perception of the company's services and will have a certain impact on the image of the company. Each employee should be allowed to actively participate in business management decisions to truly master the staff (Allen, 2020).

Therefore, it is very important to improve the consumer communication system after the completion of sales and services and to take the initiative to return visits. Companies should pay attention to the whole process of providing services to users through interactive communication to understand the feelings of customers in the process, so that customers become participants in the service marketing process, so as to improve their own services to meet customer expectations in a timely manner.

According to Goodman (2014), the highest percentage of customers complain when they are dissatisfied and decide to buy the product or service again when they are satisfied with the outcome of the problem. The customer who complains will buy this item again, even if he or she is dissatisfied. Goodman (2014) said that some customers will continue to buy the product if the manufacturer solves the problem, even if they are not satisfied with the product they purchased. Among dissatisfied customers, those who are satisfied with the outcome of the complaint are much more likely to decide to buy the product again than those who are dissatisfied but do not complain.

The customer service system will improve to enhance consumer satisfaction. Consumers are usually confronted with a large number of products and services that can satisfy a specific need. Satisfied customers repeat their purchases and tell others about their good experiences, while dissatisfied customers complain, disparage the products, and turn to competitors. In addition, when using social media, brand-related information posted in the circle of friends may help increase attention to the brand's advertising campaign, thus enhancing the effectiveness of the campaign, and likewise, word-of-mouth communication after purchase creates a chain reaction for traditional marketing communication activities (Batra & Keller, 2016).

Significance of the Study

Combined with the actual situation of the research object, the marketing data and marketing strategy are analyzed, and relevant theories and theories of marketing are applied to reveal the relevance of the marketing process so as to provide a certain reference basis for enriching marketing strategies and promoting marketing execution, which has relatively important research significance.

According to the actual characteristics of traditional marketing and Internet marketing, through comparison and analysis, to explore the effect of the traditional marketing and Internet marketing cooperation, and in the process of the implementation of the marketing strategy, identify problems and perfect, hope to find ways to improve the product sales and marketing of the effective combination, provide a more effective reference basis for related industries (Haşiloğlu, 2009).

Selecting representative enterprises is one way to study the differences between traditional marketing methods and network marketing methods and find out the changes brought by marketing strategies through data analysis. The research conclusion will provide suggestions and help similar industries and enterprises develop marketing strategies.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The research scope is limited: the research object and the research industry are both single; only for agriculture and related industries, selected research objects have certain limitations. The research data focused on the running time before and after the implementation of the program. The data can only represent the performance of the surveyed enterprises in this time period and cannot represent the generality of the industry. Some data cannot be counted objectively. They are subjective and empirical. In addition, as an ordinary small agricultural enterprise, the accounting data and management data of this enterprise are not particularly detailed, and the data provided also has certain limitations for the research.

Mainly using the literature method and case analysis, the use of research methods is limited. Relevant theories of Internet marketing are not particularly rich, and many of them are analyzed on the basis of traditional marketing theories. Therefore, there are certain limitations in the theoretical application and related literature.

Methodology

Research Design

Based on the actual needs of the paper, under the guidance of relevant theories combined with enterprise research, through data analysis, field observation, comprehensive analysis, and other methods, the author studies and analyzes the market problems of sample companies from different perspectives. In the research process of this paper, the following research methods are mainly involved:

1. Literature research method. This paper first reads relevant literature according to the research content, including classic marketing theory, Internet marketing, agricultural product marketing, Internet behavior, and social media marketing, through the collection of references and data collection to prepare for the research.

2. Case study. This study investigated the situation of sample enterprises before and after using the Internet for marketing planning. With the marketing data of enterprises for many years, the actual situation of the enterprise's marketing mode, marketing strategy, and marketing effect is studied.

3. Comprehensive analysis method. The research in this paper takes Internet marketing as the background, combines it with the development trend of current academic research, and makes comprehensive use of marketing theory, Internet application technology, human resource management, and other related theories to ensure the actual needs of the research process. Through the analysis of the actual situation of the sample companies, the relevant strategies and suggestions for the company to carry out online marketing of agricultural products are sorted out, the situation before and after the implementation of online marketing by enterprises is summarized, and the research conclusions are drawn comprehensively.

Research Procedure

The background and significance of the topic are introduced. According to the current status of agricultural-related industries in marketing, the research questions of this paper are put forward, and the research direction and scope are determined.

Determine the sample enterprises, analyze them, and summarize the status quo of the enterprises. Through the study of the sample enterprises, the characteristics, strengths, and weaknesses of the enterprises are found, and the difficulties encountered by the enterprises are found, so as to find the existing problems in the marketing of enterprises.

Formulate strategies and implement new marketing strategies in combination with the enterprise. In order to help enterprises solve marketing problems through analysis, develop new marketing programs. Apply the new scheme to the real marketing process and analyze the actual marketing data. Demonstrate the effect of the scheme. Summarize the changes and existing problems after implementation and put forward corresponding suggestions.

Results and Discussion

The marketing data and management data in this study were obtained from the actual research of the company. The final statistics of the study are the data from the sample companies. The company has made significant changes under the guidance of the new marketing program, but what are the actual results?

Analysis of fruit sales data

The analysis is based on the main products of the company, and the main sales data are as follows: Because agricultural products are affected by weather, market conditions, and other factors, production and product quality may fluctuate, so the analysis process uses data such as sales speed, wholesale volume, retail volume, and Internet sales volume to conduct analysis.

Table 1. Data analysis of pears

Year	Retail (%)	Wholesale (%)	Picking (%)	Network Sales (%)	Total sales (RMB)
2016	13.16	79.47	5.26	2.11	3,654,000
2017	21.52	63.98	8.60	5.90	3,750,000
2018	24.24	58.67	9.18	7.91	4,339,000
2019	21.59	60.68	8.64	9.09	4,574,000
2020	23.40	59.20	3.20	14.20	4,353,000

Due to the implementation of the network marketing program, the enterprise, through enterprise full marketing combined with the network platform, began to try to implement it in 2016. In 2017, with the full implementation, the effect was very obvious; sales increased a lot. However, in 2020, it decreased significantly.

The proportion of retail sales increased year by year, wholesale volume decreased, picking volume increased, and internet sales increased, especially during the pandemic period, when tourism revenue decreased significantly. Because of internet promotion and the application of the previous internet channels, sales through the internet increased. Total sales increased year by year, and the duration of sales decreased.

The increase in retail sales is due to the increase in the number of tourists visiting the farm and the increase in the number of tourists participating in rural tourism, which increases the sales volume of the farm's sales store, especially during traditional festivals and tours organized by the farm. The farm marketing team, using WeChat, has established many marketing communities. Each of which is an accurate

customer, allowing for accurate marketing and better pre-sales, sales, and post-sales, resulting in a large retail volume.

Due to the increase in brand awareness and the efforts of the sales team, they have increased the number of group orders from companies, which has also contributed to sales. At the same time, due to the continuous internet publicity, the farm became more and more famous and more and more visitors, which led to an increase in the picking volume. According to the farm’s experience, the picking volume could be bigger, but the area of the picking area was purposely controlled because of the damage to the farm vegetation and land caused by too many picking visitors. As a result of the addition of Internet and travel sales, the volume of sales increased in the same period of time, which directly affected the speed of sales and eventually led to a decrease in sales duration. It also accelerated the return on sales and increased the cash utilization rate of the company.

Table 2. The time required to complete the sale

Year	Total production of pears	Sales time
2016	380,000	130
2017	372,000	106
2018	392,000	106
2019	440,000	110
2020	384,000	150

As shown from the table above, the increase in sales speed has led to a decrease in sales duration, and another change is that the time for enterprises to use cold storage has been shortened. Previously, during the whole sales cycle, cold storage started from when the fruits were picked and stored according to the weather conditions and fruit storage requirements, and from August of the year to when the fruits were sold, it usually took five to six months for cold storage to be used, including the total time for large cold storage and the total time for small cold storage. By improving the speed of sales, the use of cold storage is shortened. Among them, the golden pear’s cold storage use time was reduced from more than 130 days to more than 110 days, of which full-load operation needs about 60 days. After marketing reform, the golden pear sales time is shortened to about three months; full-load operation only needs about 30 days. In the sales process, through the partition management of the cold storage, only part of the equipment is run, which greatly reduces the electricity consumption and equipment maintenance costs.

Sales data of cooperative products

Every year, after the sales period of the orchard, there is a slow season, during which the farm uses a cooperative model to find businesses that will cooperate in selling high-quality fruits. The varieties sold are those that are popular in the market and are not grown by our own companies.

Table 3. Total annual sales of fruits (2017-2020)

Products	Sales amount (RMB)
Orange	397,600
Ehime Orange	545,200
Grapes	521,900

The above sales are done through online reservations through the branded WeChat group run by the company. The pre-sale information is released in advance, the consumer pays the prepayment (sometimes the full amount) to the company administrator, the company contacts the partner farm, the partner farm picks and delivers the fruit directly, and upon arrival at the place of receipt, the sales department of our farm directly arranges for the delivery personnel to deliver the fruit to the destination specified by the consumer. This way, we can guarantee the best taste and freshness. This method, because

it is paid in advance or in full, can ignore the financial pressure, and there is no pressure on the goods, collection period, or even product loss, which brings the most direct benefits to the enterprise.

Tourism Revenues

Because of the increasing publicity, more and more people know about the farm, and in addition to the picking activities implemented by the farm itself, there are also many third-party tourism projects. Operating companies actively contact the farm, hoping to cooperate in holding various activities. The income obtained from these projects is as follows:

Table 4. List of projects with single lease charge

Event	Single lease charge (RMB)
Chrysanthemum Festival	50,000
Kite Festival	40,000
Light Show	50,000
Food Festival	50,000
Reptile Exhibition (model)	80,000
Scarecrow Cultural Festival	60,000
Summer Beer Festival	100,000

The list shows some of the cooperative projects and cooperative fees for years 2016-2020. In five years, the total income for the farm was 900,000 RMB. In 2019, the income was significantly reduced and in 2020, the activity was stopped.

Table 5. Space rental (in years)

Year	Space rental (RMB)
2016	50,000
2017	200,000
2018	350,000
2019	300,000
2020	0

Other fruits, such as apricots, peaches, strawberries, and persimmons, are not the main products of the farm, and the farm does not have detailed statistics. However, they bring a lot of visitors to the farm. The increase in visitors also brings sales of farm-related products, such as barbecue equipment rentals, ingredient and consumable sales, and other tourism equipment rentals.

Table 6. Picking tickets

Fruits	Ticket price	Number of people	Revenue (RMB)
Pears	20	35,000	700,000
Cherry	40	15,000	600,000

From 2016 to 2020, the cumulative sales of the two projects were about 727,000 RMB. Through statistics, visitors with membership cards can visit the park for free: fishing, picking, and free flower viewing. The project is more popular, but the holder reflects that some projects are not perfect, visitors have great opinions, affecting the experience, and finally the project was stopped.

Table 7. Sales of farm tour cards in 2016-2020

Type	Price	Total sales	Total sales (RMB)
A	200	1,000	200,000
B	350	1,500	525,000
			727,000

The projects listed above are new forms of projects developed on the basis of the existing farm, reflecting the play to drive sales and experience to drive the brand on the basis of minimal investment to achieve revenue. In 2019 and 2020, the tourism industry was particularly affected by the pandemic, so there was basically no income from tourism projects in 2020, but the advantages of online marketing came to the fore, and the proportion of sales from online marketing increased significantly, ensuring that sales were smoothly carried out through express delivery and community distribution. In addition, product collaboration with partners and online sales have enabled the farm to achieve significant sales revenue even during the low season.

Network branding data

Table 8. Network branding data

Projects	Views (*10000)
Reptile Outdoor Model Exhibition	1.7
Scarecrow Cultural Festival	3.7
Outdoor Fishing Competition	0.9
Firefly Cultural Exhibition	1
Chrysanthemum Festival	0.5
New Year Temple Festival	11
Pear Festival	0.7+3.2
Opera and Culture Festival	1.1
Cherry Festival	3.1
Summer Festival	0.4
Picking Festival	1.5
Membership Recruitment	1

The independent Internet marketing system established by the enterprise, suitable for their own needs, refines the network marketing team, improves the enterprise marketing system, enhances marketing capacity, and improves the competitiveness of the industry. In the marketing process, through experience marketing, sharing marketing, and word-of-mouth marketing, the company has achieved the effect of spreading the information of the company, allowing potential users to understand the corporate brand and product information, thus forming a purchase behavior. Due to the company's own corporate attributes and brand advantages, this kind of communication is more targeted and can win more trust and goodwill. Through the marketing reform, the farm is not only better in management but also in service, after-sales service, sales channels, and brand promotion, all of which have been well improved to achieve the enterprise's objectives.

Chinese traditional enterprises, especially agriculture-related enterprises, are facing the opportunities and challenges brought by the Internet, and the relevant enterprises need to integrate their existing resources in order to bring out their maximum advantages. Internet marketing provides more options for marketing-related enterprises, thus helping them to develop in a healthy and orderly manner. With the help of Internet tools, enterprises can have a better service experience, better service results, and achieve rapid word-of-mouth communication. It plays an active role in branding, product promotion, customer conversion, sales, and service.

Although the Internet has flooded every aspect of our lives and has a very important position, it is not a panacea. We need to have the corresponding management thinking, management model, and talent structure, but also around the consumer and the research market, to provide consumers with products that meet market demand and provide a quality consumer experience. Internet marketing is only part of the optimization of business operations and cannot completely replace the traditional marketing model. Marketing is an innovative activity; to get better results, we must maintain innovation and vitality, constantly change the concept in line with the times, and design our own marketing methods.

In the process of designing network information, we should focus on the alignment of products with the times, in terms of pictures, texts, and videos, to spread the brand information of the company through diverse communication channels. In the entire marketing system, offline marketing still has unique advantages; these advantages, whether now or in the future, cannot be completely replaced by Internet marketing, so the effective integration of the online and offline marketing models into one is still the direction that enterprises need to focus on. Through the study, we learned that the company has gotten good results after using the new marketing methods, but at the same time, we found that the company still has some problems that need to be improved, such as:

1. Insufficient staff professionalism from the level of social media operation staff, the company is still lacking in social media marketing operation human resources. For example, in marketing planning, innovation has been lacking in the planning of activities, and activities have become redundant, so there is no effect on the marketing activities to push the new. In addition, the network publicity of some software operations is not skilled, and the corresponding training mechanism is not sound.

2. The company needs to further improve the social media marketing matrix. The company mainly relies on WeChat and its circle of friends and is overly dependent on WeChat marketing. It should slowly shift its product marketing to a large sales platform and give full play to the potential of social media marketing.

3. Lack of control mechanisms for negative information. The Internet is a double-edged sword; the word-of-mouth effect can bring good reputation and customers for the company, but it can also make a fool of the enterprise, spreading the negative image of the enterprise. During the enterprise operation, some negative events will also occur, and the information will spread in the form of fission. For example, consumers who are not satisfied with the taste or quality of the product or who are not satisfied with attending live events will post this negativity on social media so that more people can see the negative news, which brings serious damage to the company's reputation.

4. Improve data analysis capability. Through data analysis, it helps companies find precise customers and continuously follow up with them to guide the marketing team, which can also improve the overall service quality of the company.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The Internet is not omnipotent; the essence of business is to provide consumers with differentiated products and a better experience. Internet marketing only improves some aspects of traditional business operations but does not completely replace the traditional marketing model. In practice, the online sales channels and publicity channels used by enterprises are narrow, so they should improve the online marketing matrix, strengthen the marketing function of social media, and increase the publicity and promotion of e-commerce platforms such as ShakeYin, Xiaohongshu, Taobao, Jingdong, Meituan, and Hungry.

The researcher suggests improving the organizational guarantee of social media marketing in response to the existence of human resources problems and cultivating professional agricultural marketing

talents. On the one hand, through the organization of training classes on agricultural technology and marketing skills, the overall awareness level of farmers can be improved, so that farmers can fully feel the importance of Internet technology in improving the efficiency and quality of agricultural production and agricultural sales (Heang et al., 2015).

We need to build a special organizational structure to ensure the smooth promotion of social media marketing. We can invite professionals to conduct e-commerce training to improve the marketing level of network operators and ensure the high-quality implementation of work related to the marketing of agricultural products. To pay attention to customer service, employees should attend after-sales service-related training, strengthen communication with customers, establish long-term relationships with customers, pay attention to online staff training and fan maintenance, and provide timely, accurate, and detailed responses to questions raised by consumers that can effectively improve consumer satisfaction and greatly influence the purchase decisions of ordinary consumers.

In terms of online opinion management mechanisms, consumers are not satisfied with the end of their purchases; they are willing to share their purchases with merchants and other consumers through social media. In the face of negative comments shared by consumers, companies should improve their mechanisms for managing negative opinions. When a negative event occurs, it is better to appoint a company spokesperson to respond in a timely manner and deal with the negative issue appropriately.

Research states that negative word-of-mouth has twice the ripple effect of positive word-of-mouth (Zhang et al., 2020), so it is important to establish and improve the social media crisis warning management mechanism, monitor social media public opinion, and take effective measures quickly to prevent further deterioration of public opinion. Although this paper has made some research findings based on the actual situation of the sample companies regarding the development of Internet marketing, The paper also gives some suggestions for the development of the company at this stage. However, because of personal ability and time constraints, this paper may have some shortcomings.

The industry involved in the paper is relatively single, but different enterprises and different industries have their own characteristics that cannot be generalized. There is a need for special research for different situations, and at the same time, with the Internet coverage becoming more extensive and deeper and deeper, Internet marketing models and strategies will become more and more rich. With the continuous development of science and technology, Internet marketing has been combined with a variety of technologies, such as big data and artificial intelligence, resulting in different ways. Artificial intelligence results in different forms of applications, which require more in-depth research.

In the field of market operations, there are many large enterprises in the field of network marketing that have attempted to create different models. Quickly grasping and analyzing the habits of consumers, meeting personalized needs, and determining consumer dynamics are important elements of corporate marketing to focus on. It is to improve the modern agricultural production and management system, cultivate the agricultural Internet management system and service model, and promote the development of modern agricultural enterprises.

To promote the development of modern agricultural enterprises, it is necessary for the enterprises themselves to continuously learn, improve the agricultural practitioners' knowledge of modern agricultural management, and adjust the enterprises' talent pool and development strategies to adapt to market changes and appropriately find the right opportunities in order to seek further development and growth.

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